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A Three-Component Feature Extraction Using DDS_SE-NET for Efficient Deep Learning-Based Image Steganalysis for Real-World Images

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Abstract

Objectives: The main objective of the work is to ensure security by creating an architecture for steganalysis to detect real-world stego images. The accuracy of Major previous works using real-world datasets varies. This architecture works well with real-world datasets. **Methods:** This study introduces DDS_SE-Net (Dilated Depthwise Separable convolutions with Squeeze and Excitation-Net), a CNN-based Image Steganalysis architecture, which combines the power of Dilation and Depthwise Separable Convolutions in the Feature Extraction (FE) stage which deals with the specified issues in image steganalysis resulting in good accuracy. The introduction of the SE (Squeeze and Excitation) block adds a content-aware mechanism to weight channels adaptively. **Findings:** The results of the present study show better generalization ability, especially when used to a dataset created in the real world. Classification metrics like Accuracy and F1-score gave results around 90% when using a payload of 0.2bpp and 0.4bpp against WOW, S_UNIWARD, and HILL steganographic algorithms. The results were compared to the existing architectures with the present dataset. It shows that the dataset plays a major role in the results. **Novelty:** The study uses real-world images for experiments thus helping steganalysis in a wide range. DDS_SE-Net uses ensemble of three components in feature extraction helping in reducing memory consumption, overfitting and loss of coverage thus giving better accuracy.

Keywords: Convolution Neural Network (CNN); Separable Convolutions; Dilated Convolution; SE Block; Steganalysis

1 Introduction

Image Steganography is a technique employed to surreptitiously incorporate confidential communications within digital photos, referred to as cover images. It can be used for regular safe communication, but lawless people can also readily make use of it to carry out illicit operations that threaten social stability and national security.

The goal of steganalysis is to protect network and information security by identifying potentially harmful stego images and differentiating stego images from cover images. Steganalysis must extract features from as many distinct perspectives as feasible in order to achieve good detection. The state-of-the-art techniques that are now available mainly rely on a distributed multiscale feature extraction approach, but they produce low generalization and poor outcomes in terms of efficient computation on small-scale images. AlexNet with five convolution layers and SRNet with twelve convolution layers are used in⁽¹⁾. The study aimed to detect only the error rates. Using the BOSSBase and ALASKA#2 datasets, the study⁽²⁾ focused on the block removal technique, which addressed the reduction of computation costs. A new blended activation function for image steganalysis is introduced in⁽³⁾ to reduce the mean squared error. Images are divided into many sub-regions by the steganalysis approach in⁽⁴⁾. The usage of small block sizes removes the need for a pooling layer. The technique increases detection accuracy while lowering computing costs. The increase in dimension of features result in consumption of memory, loss of coverage and high computation cost and the previous researches did not tackle all three of the mentioned difficulties simultaneously. To address these issues, a three-component Feature extraction method is proposed in this work. This involves separable convolutions, which includes both Depth wise and Point wise convolutions for prevention of overfitting and reducing the cost of computation. This technique is applied in⁽⁵⁾⁽⁶⁾⁽⁷⁾. Dilations help in detecting features at various scales reduce the consumption of power for processing. Finally, to weigh the channels adaptively SE blocks⁽⁸⁾ are added. While most of the previous studies used existing datasets, the real-world dataset is used in this study which helps in a wide range of applications.

2 Methodology

In this research, a DDS_SE-Net method of extracting features is proposed using dilation and employed a separable convolution to detect the stego images. During the process of producing the output feature maps, the network gives equal weight to each of its numerous channels. SE blocks to aid in the incorporation of a content-aware technique that allows for the adaptive weighting of each channel. The following sections elaborate on the concept of dilation and the formation of separable convolution and SE blocks that are used in the proposed model.

2.1 Dilated Convolution

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) use dilated convolution, sometimes referred to as atrous convolution, a sort of convolution operation that allows the network to have a bigger receptive field without expanding the number of parameters. It is identical to convolution but uses pixel skipping to cover a greater portion of the input. The mathematical formulation of Dilated convolution is shown in Equation (1).

Consider $F: \mathbb{Z}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as a discrete function. Let $\Omega_r = [-r, r] \cap \mathbb{Z}^2$. Let $k: \Omega_r \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a discrete filter. Its size is given as $(2r + 1)^2$. Let l be the dilation factor. Then $*_l$ is defined as

$$(F *_l k)(p) = \sum_{(s+lt=p)} F(s)k(t) \quad (1)$$

It is referred to as dilated convolution at summation when $l > 1$ given by Equation (1). Wavelet decomposition is the source of the concept of dilated convolution. In⁽⁹⁾, a hybrid dilated CNN is developed to address the detail loss problem, and a dilated CNN is introduced to lower the use of computing resources. When compared to traditional CNN, the MNIST handwritten dataset and the remote sensing image dataset demonstrated a good reduction in processing time and an increase in accuracy. The morphological feature maps and the original hyperspectral data are concatenated in⁽¹⁰⁾. The CNN structure enhances network performance without adding to network complexity by using both dilated and classic convolution. Hyperspectral remote sensing pictures are used for the experiments. The studies worked in image classification based on remote sensing images and proved good accuracy and reduced time consumption. A stego noise extraction module was developed specifically for steganalysis in the SNE network⁽¹¹⁾. This module consists of a reversed bottleneck layer and a paired dilated convolutional layer. This specific architecture enhances the receptive region of the network, hence augmenting the globality and flexibility of stego noise extraction to the content of the image. Even though dilated convolution is a classic technique, it has shown success in recent research. In the present investigation, real-time datasets with widely varied dimensions and colors were employed, and dilated convolution was applied to provide good accuracy. By varying dilation rates, multi-scale data is aggregated which is a novel feature applied.

2.2 Depth-wise separable convolution

Depth-wise separable convolutions have been found to mitigate overfitting and offer computational efficiency by giving good accuracy due to their reduced processing requirements, rendering them appropriate for a broader range of applications. It uses

two convolutions namely Depthwise and Pointwise convolutions as shown in Figure 1 (a) and (b). Total Multiplication is given in Equation (4). In Depthwise convolutions, assume the size of the input image is $A_i \times A_i$ and M is the number of channels. Filters of size $A_f \times A_f \times 1$, then output size will be $A_o \times A_o \times M$. Then the cost of this process will be

$$= M \times A_f^2 \times A_o^2 \tag{2}$$

In Pointwise convolutions, the Convolution applied is 1×1 on M Channels. Thus, the output size would be $A_o \times A_o \times N$. Then the cost of this process will be

$$= M \times A_o^2 \times N \tag{3}$$

Total Multiplications of Depthwise and Pointwise convolutions = Equation (2) + Equation (3)

$$= M \times A_f^2 \times A_o^2 + M \times A_o^2 \times N$$

$$= M \times A_o^2 (A_f^2 + N) \tag{4}$$

This operation performs N times lesser multiplication than normal Convolutions.

Fig 1. (a) Depth-wise Separable Convolutions (b) Pointwise Separable convolutions

2.3 SE Block

The Squeeze-and-Excitation Block as shown in Figure 2 facilitates dynamic channel-wise feature recalibration for the network. Since the SE block can acquire feature weights to create valid effective feature maps with big weights and ineffective feature maps with low weights, it increases the detection accuracy rate. In convolutional vision transducer CVTStego-Net⁽¹²⁾ to reduce the impact of redundant data and boost sensitivity in steganographic noise, the noise extraction and analysis stage incorporates SE-Block with residual operations. In the classification stage, SE-Block is combined with a convolutional vision converter to connect both the local and global spatial connections of the steganographic noise.

Fig 2. Flow Diagram of Squeeze and Excitation block

2.4 DDS_SE-Net architecture

There are three segments as given in Figure 3. The front segment is responsible for processing the data and minimizing the noise residuals; the central segment aims at lowering the dimensions of the feature maps involving an ensemble of dilated convolution with depth-wise separable convolutions and SE blocks; and the final section, which is a typical fully connected layer meant for flattening, continued by a Sigmoid node.

2.4.1 The pre-processing segment

The images acquired are real-world images. So, they vary greatly in size, dimension, and texture. So, the collected images are pre-processed and made to be of the same size and dimension. Now they are ready to be fed to the next stage.

2.4.2 The feature extraction segment

There are three groups of layers in the feature extraction stage. Each group has a dilated Convolution layer with kernels of size 5*5 and stride (1, 1) followed by Batch Normalization. Then the Depthwise Convolutions followed by Separable convolution layer of kernel size 3*3 with Depthwise and Pointwise convolutions. This layer is followed by the SE block which uses shortcuts with multiplication ending with max Pooling of size (2, 2). The activation function in Convolution layers is ReLu because it yields good performances, and its gradient computation is fast. In SE blocks both ReLu and Sigmoid are involved.

2.4.3. The classification segment

The features extracted from the above segment are fed to the classification module which consists of 2 fully connected layers. There are 64 neurons in the first layer and two neurons in the last completely linked layer, which is equal to the number of classes in the output of the network. This module concludes with the production of an allocation over the two class labels using a sigmoid activation function.

Fig 3. Flowchart of DDS_SE-Net

3 Results and Discussion

The experiments were conducted on a real-world dataset collected online which has 5000 images (Cover). Stego images were created using three spatial steganographic algorithms WOW⁽¹³⁾, HILL⁽¹⁴⁾ and S-UNIWARD⁽¹⁵⁾ with payload 0.4bpp and 0.2bpp. 4000 image pairs were used for training and 1000 pairs for testing and the results were tabulated. The stego images created along with the cover images as shown in Figure 4 were fed to the network architecture and the results were tabulated. Table 1 displays the outcomes of the DDS_SE-Net for the WOW, S-UNIWARD, and HILL steganography algorithms. For comparison, 0.4 and 0.2bpp payloads were used. The results show that the architecture works better against WOW than the other algorithms. A comparison of the proposed architecture's accuracy with three steganographic methods is shown in Figure 5. Table 2 shows how the proposed framework stands out from the two earlier CNNs, Yedroutdj-net⁽¹⁶⁾ and GBRAS-net⁽¹⁷⁾. The important point here is that the real-world dataset was used for experiments in the present study while the other architectures used existing steganography datasets for their earlier work. The results that are shown are from Testing. The comparison of the metrics like Accuracy, precision, Recall, and F1-score with the earlier architectures is shown in Figure 6. DDS_SE-Net shows an increase in accuracy and a decrease in loss when compared with the other architectures using real world dataset. Figure 7 depicts the decrease in loss using the present study compared with the previous works.

GBRAS-net gave 89.8% accuracy on WOW with 0.4bpp, 87.1% accuracy on S-UNIWARD, and 81.9% on HILL. Yedroutdj-net gave 85.1% accuracy on WOW and 77.4% on S-UNIWARD while the study (2) produced 90.73% accuracy. All these studies used the standard BOSSBase dataset for their experiments. With the real-world dataset in the present study, GBRAS-net produced an accuracy of 84.1% and 82.3 % against WOW and S-UNIWARD respectively. Yedroutdj-net produced an accuracy of 74.3% and 74.6% against WOW and S-UNIWARD respectively. The reduction in accuracy shows that the dataset plays a major role in results. Moreover, the novel DDS_SE-net with three component feature extraction including Separable convolutions, Dilations, and SE block gave 92.9% and 89.2% accuracy against WOW and S-UNIWARD with 0.4bpp using a real-world dataset which is high compared to the existing architectures by reducing the overfitting problem and loss of coverage. This also helps in reducing memory consumption.

Fig 4. Image samples of (a) Cover (b) Stego using WOW 0.4bpp (c) Stego using S-Uniward 0.4bpp (d) Stego using HILL 0.4bpp

Table 1. Evaluation Metrics of DDS_SE-Net against WOW, S-UNIWARD, and HILL with 0.4bpp and 0.2bpp

Steganographic algorithm	Payload	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 score (%)	Loss (%)
WOW	0.4bpp	92.9	91.5	94.0	92.7	21.0
S_UNIWARD		89.2	91.4	86.9	89.0	31.9
HILL		89.8	91.5	87.9	89.6	30.3
WOW	0.2bpp	93.2	91.5	94.0	92.7	21.0
S_UNIWARD		89.0	90.4	87.9	89.1	30.0
HILL		90.7	91.9	90.4	91.1	18.0

Fig 5. Comparison of metrics of DDS_SE-Net against WOW, S-UNIWARD and HILL with 0.4bpp and 0.2bpp

Table 2. Evaluation Metrics of DDS_SE-Net in comparison with other CNN steganalysis architectures against WOW, S-UNIWARD and HILL with 0.4bpp

Architecture	Steganographic algorithm	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 score (%)	Loss (%)
Yedroudj-net	WOW	74.3	77.2	73.2	75.1	58.0
	S_UNIWARD	74.6	76.1	74.3	75.2	56.0
	HILL	74.6	74.2	76.7	75.5	58.0
GBRAS-net	WOW	84.1	84.9	83.6	84.2	37.1
	S_UNIWARD	82.3	83.0	81.8	82.4	38.0
	HILL	84.5	84.6	84.6	84.6	40.0
DDS_SE-net	WOW	92.9	91.5	94.0	92.7	21.0
	S_UNIWARD	89.2	91.4	86.9	89.0	31.9
	HILL	89.8	91.5	87.9	89.6	30.3

Fig 6. Comparison of Evaluation Metrics of DDS_SE-Net with other architectures against WOW, S-UNIWARD and HILL with 0.4bpp

Fig 7. Comparison of Loss of DDS_SE-Net with other architectures against WOW, S-UNIWARD and HILL with 0.4bpp

It is evident from Table 3 that DDS_SE-Net has 33.4% fewer trainable parameters than Traditional CNN. The model using DDS_SE-Net is only two-thirds the size of the model using standard CNN. DDS_SE-Net takes approximately 27.7% less time than the model using Conventional CNN to evaluate. Because DDS_SE-Net takes fewer operations to create a prediction, its 1.179 billion FLOPs make it computationally more efficient. It uses less power and completes inference more quickly. The effective receptive field is increased by spatially expanding the kernel by dilated convolution. This increases accuracy but might slightly increase the computational cost. There comes Depth wise separable convolutions that reduce the number of parameters needed by splitting a standard convolution into two phases and reduce the cost of computation. Combining these two methods allows the network to gather more data, improve accuracy and efficiency, and use fewer parameters.

Table 3. The performance improvement of DDS_SE-Net (Compared with Traditional CNN)

CNN	Time required	Number of Trainable Parameters	Model size	FLOPs
Traditional CNN	219.46 seconds	1,969,359	23409.66 kilo bytes	1.866 billion
DDS_SE-net	171.89 seconds	1,311,999	15657.45 kilo bytes	1.179 billion

4 Conclusion

This study suggests a CNN-based image steganalysis model that produces noteworthy outcomes given that the architectures offer advancements with superior categorization capabilities. DDS_SE-Net architecture performs better for real-world image steganalysis than other networks. Three major components, that is the dilation, separable convolution, and SE blocks components are used by the CNN. This solves the problems of increased memory usage, and overfitting which could be noted from good accuracy. Additionally, SE blocks aid in the adaptive weighting of the channels and improve accuracy, a crucial steganalysis statistic. The suggested CNN has remarkably good steganographic image detection. Since most of the earlier studies dealt with image databases that were already accessible for steganography, this work permits the incorporation of a new database (real-world data) into the spatial realm. In comparison to the previous architectures, the newly developed DDS_SE-net with three-component feature extraction gave 92.9% and 89.2% accuracy as opposed to WOW and S-UNIWARD with 0.4bpp. The overall results demonstrate that the new design is more accurate on real world dataset than the prior ones. There are also few limitations too like Depthwise separable convolutions might tend to underfit and slightly reduces accuracy as it lowers parameters. This is compensated by the usage of dilations. Future research will focus on delving further into the other available datasets and examining the workings of this architecture. In addition, fresh methods will be applied to enhance the feature extraction phase. Perhaps this work in the future will improve CNN architecture's grading capabilities.

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